

Impact of sintering temperature variation on the structural and electrical properties of praseodymium modified $\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Ti}_{0.90}\text{O}_3$ ceramics

Ramovatar¹, Indrani Coondoo², S. Satapathy³ and Neeraj Panwar^{1,*}

¹Department of Physics, Central University of Rajasthan, Bandarsindri, Ajmer-305817, Rajasthan, India

²Department of Physics & CICECO- Aveiro Institute of Materials, University of Aveiro, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

³Laser Material Section, HBNI, Raja Ramanna Centre for Advanced Technology, Indore- 452013, India

* Corresponding author's email: neerajpanwar@curaj.ac.in

Abstract

Rare-earth ions like praseodymium (Pr) substitution has been shown to enhance the electrical properties of lead free piezoelectrics [1 – 4]. The effect of sintering temperature variation (1350 – 1450 °C) on the structural, ferroelectric and dielectric properties of 0.04 wt% Pr_6O_{11} -doped $\text{Ba}_{0.85}\text{Ca}_{0.15}\text{Ti}_{0.9}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{O}_3$ (BCZT) ceramics has been studied systematically. The results demonstrated that structural and electrical properties of Pr modified BCZT samples are strongly sintering temperature dependent. XRD results confirmed co-existing tetragonal and orthorhombic phases at all sintering temperatures with maximum tetragonality at 1400 °C. Further, the average Ti – O bond length decreases with increasing sintering temperatures. Similar observations were made from the Raman spectra. The highest ferroelectric ($2P_r \sim 21.6 \mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) and dielectric ($\epsilon_m \sim 8805, \tan\delta \sim 0.032$) properties were observed for Pr doped BCZT compound sintered at 1400 °C. The electrical properties are explained on the basis of crystallite size, density, tetragonality and bond length of these ceramics. It is concluded from the present study that optimal properties of 0.04 wt% Pr_6O_{11} -doped BCZT can be achieved at 1400 °C sintering temperature.

Keywords: Lead free ceramics; Ferroelectric properties; Dielectrics properties

References

1. I. Coondoo, N. Panwar, H. Amorin, V.E. Ramana, M. Alguero and A. Kholkin, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 98 (2015) 3127.
2. I. Coondoo, N. Panwar, R. Vidyasagar and A.L. Kholkin, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 18 (2016) 31184.
3. Ramovatar, I. Coondoo, S. Satapathy and N. Panwar, *Ceram. Int.* (2017), In Press, doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.10.097.
4. Q. Zhang, H. Sun, X. Wang, Y. Zhang and X. Li, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 34 (2014) 1439.